

IMPROVE-HF RESEARCH COMMUNITY

NEWSLETTER

NOVEMBER 2025

WELCOME TO THE
FIRST EDITION OF THE IMPROVE-HF NEWSLETTER

We're excited to share our work to improve heart failure care in Wales.

IMPROVE-HF, an NIHR-funded project, unites public contributors, healthcare professionals, and researchers to lay the groundwork for a future NIHR application focused on early diagnosis and better outcomes.

More information can be found [here](#).

Not yet part of our research community? Scan the QR code or click the [link](#) below to join us today!

PROJECT UPDATES

Survey

We shared our research capacity and culture survey, thank you to everyone who's responded. If you haven't yet, please share your views by completing it [here](#) or scanning the QR code.

Public Contributors

We're thrilled to welcome seven public contributors to IMPROVE-HF. Their experiences will help ensure the voices of those affected by heart failure are central to our work.

Monthly Meetings

Our core research team meet monthly to discuss project progress. We have added an open-session to the end of each meeting so that those in our wider heart failure community can now connect with us, share ideas and explore opportunities to get more involved.

Work Package 3

Data extraction and initial analysis are complete, and early results will be presented as a poster at the British Society for Heart Failure meeting (20-21 November 2025). The poster will be shared in the next newsletter.

'SANDPIT' EVENT SUMMARY

Our “sandpit” event at Swansea University on the 16th September was a great success, bringing together 27 researchers, healthcare professionals, public contributors, and partners to shape the future of heart failure care in Wales.

During the event attendees:

Summarised their heart failure services

Investigated causes of poor heart failure outcomes

Prioritised key factors for improvement

Developed innovative solutions to the identified problems

Most important topics discussed according to respondents

- Variation and inequality in heart failure services across Wales
- Early detection, diagnosis, and prevention of heart failure
- Collaboration, innovation and research

Feedback

Response rate: 67% (18 responses)

83% of respondents rated the event **excellent**

1st Respondents found the **problem-framing activity** most useful, rating the session **4.22/5**

2nd Respondents found the **service mapping talks** the second most useful session, rating the session **4.11/5**

“I thought the event was illuminating, thought-provoking and reassuring in that everyone was committed to enhancing access and delivery.”

Next Steps

We are now working to prioritise which of the proposed interventions/innovations is included in WP2 - the systematic review.

Welcoming our Public Contributors

We have seven public contributors on the IMPROVE-HF project. Their insights, experiences, and perspectives will play a vital role in shaping our research and ensuring it remains relevant and impactful for the communities we serve.

Public Contributor Spotlight

Carol Barrett

"As someone with heart failure who has struggled to access NHS care, I want to help shape a Wales-wide strategy for service improvement. Talking with local health professionals and others exploring service models has deepened my understanding of the current situation"

Latest Advances in Heart Failure Research

[Effectiveness of tirzepatide in patients with HFpEF using a target trial emulation retrospective cohort study.](#)
Nature Communications

Spotlight: Tirzepatide Shows Promising Benefits for HFpEF Patients

A new open-access study in Nature Communications (May 2025) suggests tirzepatide could play an important role in treating heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), particularly in patients with obesity or metabolic disease.

Researchers compared more than 14,000 people taking tirzepatide with similar patients who were not treated with the drug. Over one year, patients receiving tirzepatide had about a 50% lower chance of being hospitalized for heart failure or dying from any cause. The benefits were seen across different ages, sexes, and levels of kidney function.

These real-world findings support earlier trial results and strengthen the case for considering tirzepatide in appropriate HFpEF patients, especially those where weight and metabolic control are key priorities.

As treatment for HFpEF continues to evolve, this study provides timely evidence that a metabolic-focused approach may improve outcomes in routine practice, not just clinical trials.

Events of Interest

National Cardiovascular Research Network
Rhydwaith Cenedlaethol Ymchwil Gardiofasgwlaidd

National Cardiovascular Research Network (NCRN) Meeting 2025

Location: National Museum Cardiff

Date: December 4th 2025

This event aims to bring together researchers, clinicians, allied health professionals and others interested in cardiovascular research across Wales. The meeting will introduce what the NCRN can offer its members and provide a valuable opportunity to connect, collaborate and share ideas.

Attendees will also have the chance to showcase posters of their research, creating a forum for cross-disciplinary and cross-institutional networking. Please follow this [link](#) to register.

